

State of the art impact models

D5.1: State of the art impact models
WP 5

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1 Introduction

1.1 Role of impact models in the overall concept of DISTENDER

This document provides a description of the DISTENDER impact models. It is to be understood as a working document, which will be updated and augmented within the course of the DISTENDER project to provide a suitable source of reference for the current and future user of the DISTENDER products and DISTENDER DSS. The main purpose of this document is to provide information on the potentials and limits of the impact models in an easily understandable form. The full documentation of the impact models goes beyond this document and is given in the appropriate technical and scientific description of the models used. Thus, this document is limited to the essential aspects of the model description in the context of DISTENDER. The impact models provide tools to assess the impact of changing climate, socio-economic development and coping-strategies upon the relevant socio-economic and environmental parameters. They also facilitate a link between the different climate scenarios analysed and the adaptation and mitigation approaches defined to address these climate scenarios. The assessment of climate effects as well as the measures are based on their effects and impacts on different essential components of the environmental system. As essential components within DISTENDER we identified six sectors which are of key importance for a sustainable development of our society. These sectors are air quality, urban climate (esp. urban heat), human health, energy, water and agriculture / forestry and other types (esp. plant production). These sectors are addressed by the different impact models described in the main chapters of this document. The rationale for the selection of suitable impact models is based on a compromise between scientific complexity and robustness / applicability. Terrestrial ecosystems as well as man and environment interactions are very complex. They show many feedbacks and interactions. Particularly the inherent dependencies, such as choice of agricultural crops, economy and water demand, or the natural water supply and plant productivity or the link between air quality and human health lead to a complex system of interactions and feedbacks, which can only partially be addressed with the available disciplinary numerical models. Thus, the choice of the selected impact models was made from the practical point of view to provide a) robust information on the effects of different climate change scenarios upon the environmental parameters or environmental services and b) to provide sensitivity and responsiveness to potential adaptation and mitigation measures. Thus, the model must be responsive to the given meteorological input but also to socio-economic parameters and scenarios. The sensitivity of a given impact model to a particular parameter varies from model to model. Therefore, key parameters which drive the model or affect the model output must be identified from the perspective of climatic as well as social economic drivers. A prerequisite of the models selected for DISTENDER is the transferability and applicability of the model. A transferable and applicable approach must be scientifically sound, it must be based on generally available data and it must be available to be used in the future beyond the current application and case studies of DISTENDER.

Utilizing a range of different impact models provides a potential to systematically and coherently address different aspects of climate change and mitigation / adaptation measures. While a particular climate change effect or adaptation measure might have positive effects on some domains, it might have a negative effect on others. Also, the effects of climate change and mitigation / adaptation measures differ spatially and temporally. Thus,

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the selected impact models must be spatially and temporally explicit addressing the relevant processes and their spatial and temporal domains. The spatial and temporal representation of the model therefore may change from model to model, ranging from small scale and high-resolution assessment of specific events (e.g. urban heat waves) to continuous representation of coarse resolution (e.g. water fluxes in sub-watersheds). For the benefit of applicability and robustness, and against the background of the duration of the DISTENDER project, existing well tested models were selected. These models are typically developed from a disciplinary perspective of a clearly defined range of applications. Cross disciplinary interactions and feedbacks between the different impact models can be analysed implicitly through the assessment of the different model outcomes with the same climate drivers. However, due to the different focus of the different impact models and since the different impact models are not coupled, some existing interactions of the man-environment system in terms of natural process interactions, socio-economic process interactions or man-environment interactions may not be addressed by the impact models (e.g. impact of energy costs upon irrigation, impact of flooding upon agriculture).

In order for the results of the impact models to be coherent, the following preconditions were considered: a) utilize the same sources for model input and b) calibrate the impact model output utilizing wherever possible measured data for a past reference period and c) provide model outputs only for the disciplinary domain(s) of the impact model. Thus, the weather data used by all WP5 impact models is based on the same inputs, as produced by WP4 using a statistical down-scaling process. Another key input towards the consistency of the impact models is the use of the Corine Land Cover classification as the reference classification for the reference year 2018. In addition, the impact models are applied on the domains previously defined in D9.1 for each CCS. However, some models require a different spatial domain. The water impact model solves the water balance equation, which is only valid for watersheds. Thus, watersheds covering the major part of a CCS are used in this case, while all input data for these watersheds are again derived from the common data sources. Conversion of model output to the common raster is possible, but not always meaningful, as in the case of discharge it is measured in a stream at selected locations. In the case of the energy impact model, the input data considers administrative boundaries instead of the previously defined domains. This adaptation was necessary because energy consumption is not usually expressed spatially, since this variable depends on the energy sector (e.g. a single industry in a specific location might have higher consumption than a larger geographic area). However, the model outputs were spatially expressed by connecting the energy sectors to the previously mentioned land use classification. Models working on regular grids use the definition of domains based on a geographical coordinate system, CCS extent and grid resolution in degrees. Finally, as for the local socio-economic scenarios (future land use and parameters), all models use the same input information, as produced by WP3. Regarding the output data, all impact models produce results with at least yearly temporal resolution (or higher), referenced with geographical coordinates.

DISTENDER models are calibrated and evaluated against observational data provided by core case studies in D9.2 or obtained from European and national databases. The evaluation results of each model are provided by the impact models, together with the results of the models. They will be reported in the next project report as the evaluation activities are concluded after the end of the first report.

Building upon the model results, strategies for mitigation and adaptation are identified and used to change inputs to the impact model or the model parameters. The effect of these mitigation and adaptation strategies can then be assessed by running the impact models utilizing different climate scenarios. The assessment of the model output provides an

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indication of a safe action corridor for adaptation and mitigation. To address the different types of model results of the different impact models, the output of the models will be translated into indicators to assess the simulated environmental and socio-economic impacts. The indicators are used also to ease communication with the case studies and as a basis for the development of robust strategies. The risk and vulnerability to the potential impacts will be evaluated in a holistic or integrated manner. Integrated assessment requires an interdisciplinary process that combines, interprets and communicates knowledge from diverse scientific disciplines as represented by the impact models. The indicators are a key element to facilitate the cross disciplinary integration and assessment.

1.2 Connection to the DSS

The impact models provide essential inputs to the decision support system (DSS) in terms of the model drivers (inputs), the essential information on the model assumptions (e.g. model description and metadata) and particularly of the model results (e.g. model parameters with their metadata). The model results will be provided to the DSS as tables, time series and/or maps. The spatial and temporal characteristics of the data provided to the DSS depend upon the impact model and its modelled output. In addition to the model output, the magnitude of change in regards to a reference model run is provided to the DSS. The percentage change and/or the absolute change of the given climate scenario or adaptation measure (and possibly also the rate of change) is often easier to understand for the decision maker as compared to the absolute value. A further simplification of the impact model output is its representation in the form of indices. Indices usually provide a qualitative assessment, typically for categories on ordinal or interval scale which may be represented on a Likert scale. In special cases, these indicators may also refer to quantitative information provided on an interval or a ratio scale. Details on the definition of the indices will be provided as a result of the further developments in DISTENDER. However, these indices will refer to a clearly defined set of reference values. For a given case study, the corridor of acceptable outcomes should be defined by the user of the DSS. The acceptable range of values or of change is location specific. Thus, the translation of (physical) model output to indicator value, should be dynamically implemented in the DSS allowing for a user specific assessment.

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2 Impact models

2.1 Emissions and air quality

2.1.1 Introduction

Air pollution is currently the most important environmental risk to human health, and it is perceived as the second biggest environmental concern for Europeans, after climate change. More than 70% of the European Union (EU) population live in urban areas, where economic activities cause high levels of air pollution.

As air pollution is strongly dependent on meteorological conditions, it is sensitive to climate change. According to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (IPCC, 2021), it is expected that climate change will have complex effects on chemistry, transport, and deposition of air pollutants.

Numerical models are primary tools for air quality assessment since they allow to characterize air quality both in time and space in an area - in contrast to the limitations in the spatial coverage of air quality measurements, to quantify the link between emissions and air pollutants concentrations, and, finally, to investigate the impact of future emission sources or alternative emission scenarios and the future impacts of climate change on air quality and health (Rafael et al., 2021). They are able to estimate the air pollutant concentrations by mathematically representing the physical and chemical processes occurring in the atmosphere under future climate and socio-economic conditions. These conditions are represented in the model by climate scenarios and emission projections, based on natural and anthropogenic activities, as the two main inputs for an air quality simulation.

2.1.2 Model description

There are different types of air quality models, and the choice of the most adequate model for a given case depends on the purpose of the modelling application and on the model specifications to meet the purpose. In the scope of DISTENDER, the selection of the air quality model is based on the flexibility to be applied to the different core case study (CCS) areas of interest which span from local to national scale, and on the compromise between complexity, requirements of computational power and resources, and running time to achieve the objectives.

2.1.2.1 Emissions

Air pollutant and greenhouse gases emissions are quantified for each CCS domain based on the EMEP (European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme) emission inventory (EMEP, 2017) available for Europe on a grid with 0.1° resolution. Following previously defined and applied methodologies (e.g. Ferreira et al, 2020; Coelho et al., 2022), the annual emissions are temporally (daily or hourly, according to CCS) and spatially (for each domain resolution) disaggregated by different proxies, adequate to each of the 11 SNAP (Selected Nomenclature for Air Pollution) activity sectors: energy production (S1), commercial and residential combustion (S2), industrial combustion and production processes (S3, S4), extraction and distribution of fossil fuels and geothermal energy (S5), solvent and other

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product use (S6), road transport (S7), off-road transport (S8), waste treatment and disposal (S9), agriculture (S10) and nature (S11).

2.1.2.2 Air Quality

The air quality for each CCS domain will be simulated by the URBAIR® second generation gaussian model, developed and extensively used by the UAVR team (Borrego et al., 2016, Rafael et al., 2021, Fernandes et al., 2021, Oliveira et al., 2022). This modelling system is designed to be modular and includes the pre-processing of geo-information, meteorological conditions and air pollutant emissions, coupled with a dispersion module.

URBAIR® provides air quality patterns for a given spatial domain (ideally with up to about 50 km from the domain centre) and time period (e.g. hourly, daily, 1 year or multiple years) for different gaseous and particulate air pollutants. The system framework is designed in a way that the inputs/outputs of the different modules are shared and linked along the modelling process. The four main modules composing the URBAIR system are:

- i. Meteorological module - to characterize the dynamics of the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) during the period of simulation and pre-process relevant meteorological parameters for the dispersion module, following the Monin–Obukhov similarity theory approach, using surface and upper air meteorological databases.
- ii. Emissions module – considers natural and anthropogenic emissions of the pollutants to be simulated in a gridded format with spatial and temporal variability.
- iii. Geo-information module – characterizes the simulation domain in terms of the terrain surface elevation, land use, emission sources location and dimension, and receptors location (for which outputs are obtained).
- iv. Dispersion module - it uses a steady-state multi-source plume air Gaussian dispersion modelling approach, where the effects of meteorological conditions, topography and the presence of buildings are considered for the transport and dispersion simulation of air pollutants within the area of interest, typically urban areas.

More details on the URBAIR® model can be found in Fernandes et al. (2021).

2.1.3 Input Data

Input data to calculate emissions are:

- EMEP atmospheric emission inventory for Europe
- Proxy data, provided by CCS or publicly available for Europe, for emission disaggregation – CORINE 2018 Land use database, population spatial distribution, Open Street Map and Open Transport Map, location of point source emissions (industry).

Input data for air quality modelling are:

- Emissions, as described above
- Meteorological surface data and vertical profiles from the statistical downscaling of climate models provided by WP4 – variables listed in the inputs table (see Annex, p.51 ff)
- Air quality monitoring data available for each CCS for air quality modelling calibration and validation

A table of the socio-economic mode inputs can be found in Annex 3.1.1.

2.1.4 Output Data

Regarding atmospheric emissions, maps of atmospheric gridded annual emissions (including the pollutants NO_x, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, CO, SO₂, VOC, NH₃, and greenhouse gases CO₂, N₂O, CH₄) for each CCS domain will be produced. An example is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Example of total NO_x emissions (Mg/year) for the Guimarães domain of 1 km resolution (GUI_D1).

For air quality, modelling results for pollutant concentrations will be calculated with an hourly or daily time step, depending on the requirements of the CCS, for each grid cell of CCS domains. The air quality outputs will be maps of annual average concentrations for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and O₃ for each CCS domain, and maps of exceedances of the air quality standards regulated by the European Commission and recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021).

A table of model outputs can be found in Annex 3.1.2.

2.1.5 Limitations

Limitations of the emissions and air quality modelling approach are mainly related to uncertainties in emission quantification and to the air quality model applied.

Emission data rely on annual emission estimates provided by Member State as a requirement of European Legislation, and thus it is dependent on the data availability, and the level of spatial and temporal detail, for each country. Moreover, the disaggregation process is based on proxy data like population distribution, road network, or land use, for which databases are available with different spatial detail, leading to uncertainties in the estimation of gridded emissions for each CCS modelling grid. Those depend on the grid cell

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size. The highest spatial resolution has the greatest uncertainty, but could be minimized if detailed CCS specific proxy data are provided. Data availability is analysed case by case. Despite the complexity behind the development of the air quality models, their results have a defined uncertainty, which is usually associated with input data (meteorological conditions and emissions rates) used in those models. Beyond that, some studies have been showing that model results are considerably sensitive to grid resolution. The studies conducted agree in their main conclusions: a coarse grid resolution may produce large discrepancies in the results compared to a fine grid resolution since it cannot capture inhomogeneity in emission rates, meteorology and land use. A fine grid may cause the simulation to be inefficient since it can be considerably limited by calculation time. Therefore, air quality studies should be performed using the appropriate grid resolution to obtain reliable and acceptable results in terms of both accuracy and computational time, selected according to the study scope (Fernandes et al., 2021 and refs therein).

As URBAIR® is a simple gaussian model, it has some limitations that will be adequately addressed in DISTENDER applications. It only considers non-reactive species because it has no chemistry included. Thus, O₃ concentrations will be estimated based on a simple chemistry module using temperature and NO₂ and VOC concentrations. In its current form, the URBAIR model considers one meteorological input per simulation domain. CCS air quality domains will be subdivided into various simulation grids to account for meteorological spatial variability. Moreover, the performance and sensitivity of URBAIR to the spatial and temporal variability of input parameters, for the different resolutions and domain sizes, will be assessed with the Round 1 simulation results.

References

The impact models on “emissions and air quality” are closely coupled to the impact model “health impacts”. Thus, the references are given in chapter 2.3.

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2.2 Urban heat

2.2.1 Introduction

Process-based numerical simulations of the urban climate can provide a cost-effective assessment of urban overheating with greater spatial and temporal resolution than in-situ observations (Nazarian et al., 2022). Importantly, numerical models allow the evaluation of potential heat hazards and an assessment of the efficacy of heat adaptation strategies (Krayenhoff et al., 2021). In recent years, numerous urban modelling tools—of different resolution, scale, level of sophistication, and suitability—have attempted to quantify the interactions between climate change and urbanization, and in particular how the urban thermal environment is shaped under their combined effect. Urban numerical models can be classified into four main categories (Nazarian et al., 2023):

1. “bulk” or “land surface models”: one-dimensional urban models where urban areas are represented as horizontal surfaces interacting with the overlying air; e.g., the UrbClim model (De Ridder et al., 2015).
2. “single-layer” urban canopy models: models based on a two-dimensional street canyon configuration; e.g., the Single Layer Urban Canopy Model (SLUCM) scheme (Kusaka et al., 2001).
3. “multilayer” urban canopy modes: models that employ several layers within the urban canopy; e.g. the Building Environment Parameterization (BEP) scheme (Martilli et al., 2002).
4. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) models: models that explicitly consider three-dimensional buildings and enable sophisticated microclimate numerical simulations of the flow inside urban canyons; e.g., the ENVI-met model (Bruse & Fler, 1998).

Land surface models are particularly useful for simulations where the model domain is large and/or significant constraints in computation capacity exist, such as in the case of regional or global climate change modelling. It is important to note that land surface models can perform fairly well when compared to other more complex urban models (Best & Grimmond, 2015).

2.2.2 Model description

The Surface Urban Energy and Water balance Scheme (SUEWS) (Järvi et al., 2011, 2014; Ward et al., 2016) is one of the most comprehensive and widely tested urban land surface models. SUEWS focuses on the local (neighbourhood) scale (typically 100 m to 1 km spatial resolution and 1 min to 1 hour temporal resolution) and simulates radiation, energy, and water balances by utilizing solely standard meteorological variables (such as air temperature, wind, and relative humidity) and information about the urban surface cover. The model is centred upon the urban energy balance (Oke et al., 2017):

$$Q^* + Q_F = Q_H + Q_E + \Delta Q_S \quad (1)$$

and the urban water balance (Grimmond et al., 1986):

$$P + I_e = E + R + \Delta S \quad (2)$$

where Q^* is the net radiation, Q_F the anthropogenic heat flux, Q_H the sensible heat flux, Q_E the latent heat flux, ΔQ_S the net storage heat flux, P precipitation, I_e the water supplied by irrigation, E the evaporation, R the runoff, and ΔS the net water storage change.

SUEWS describes the urban surface in terms of basic surface types (roads, buildings, trees, low vegetation, bare soil, and water). A wide number of parameters can be prescribed for each surface type; e.g., the height of buildings, the reflectance of urban materials or the vegetation phenology. In general, a grid cell in SUEWS consists of fractions of multiple surface types, i.e., the model utilizes a ‘multi-tile’ urban representation. Each individual surface type exerts a unique influence on the overlying atmosphere. In addition, the model can be applied to a domain that is partitioned into multiple grid cells. An overview of the main processes in SUEWS can be found in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Overview of the processes in SUEWS (Ward et al., 2016).
 With meteorological drivers: K: shortwave radiation, RH: relative Humidity, T: Temperature, U: wind Speed, P: precipitation L: longwave radiation, Q: Energy: radiation balance(*), sensible (F), evaporative (E), Soil(s)

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SUEWS has been extensively validated in multiple sites under different background climates (Alexander et al., 2016; Harshan et al., 2018; Järvi et al., 2014; Karsisto et al., 2016; Kokkonen et al., 2018; Ward et al., 2016). Results from these studies have indicated a good agreement of model simulations with in-situ observations; the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) was ranging between $16 - 45 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ for Q^* , $1 - 38 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ for Q_E , and $28 - 47 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ for Q_H .

Initially, SUEWS was developed as an improvement of the urban water balance model of Grimmond et al. (1986), with the addition of an urban evaporation-interception scheme (Grimmond & Oke, 1991). Gradually, it has incorporated various additional sub-models that allow a more accurate representation of the urban thermal environment. For instance, the Objective Hysteresis Model (OHM) (Grimmond et al., 1991) is used for the computation of ΔQ_s , the Net All-wave Radiation Parameterisation (NARP) (Offerle et al., 2003) computes radiation fluxes; the Local-scale Urban Meteorological Parameterisation Scheme (LUMPS) (Grimmond & Oke, 2002) provides an initial estimate of the atmospheric stability, while anthropogenic heat emissions are calculated taking into account population density and cooling/heating degree days (Järvi et al., 2011; Sailor & Vasireddy, 2006). For further details the reader is referred to the corresponding publications (Järvi et al., 2011; Ward et al., 2016) and the SUEWS documentation (<https://suews.readthedocs.io>).

2.2.3 Input Data

SUEWS is designed to require only basic meteorological data as input information (incoming shortwave radiation, air temperature, atmospheric pressure, relative humidity, wind speed and precipitation). If additional observed or simulated data is available (for instance, incoming longwave radiation or soil moisture) it can be directly incorporated in the model. The forcing data should be representative of the local-scale, i.e., collected or derived above the roughness sub-layer) (see Figure 3). A summary of the hourly meteorological forcing variables (derived from the statistical downscaling techniques in WP4) that will be used for the simulations of SUEWS in DISTENDER is given in Table 1.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of the Urban Boundary Layer (Oke et al., 2017).

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Table 1: Input meteorological variables for SUEWS simulations

Variable	Units	Level
Hourly average air temperature	°C	50 m
Hourly average of eastward wind	m/s	50 m
Hourly average of northward wind	m/s	50 m
Hourly average air relative humidity	%	50 m
Hourly average of air pressure	hPa	50 m
Hourly cumulative precipitation	mm	Surface
Hourly accumulated downward shortwave radiation	J/m ²	Surface
Hourly accumulated downward longwave radiation	J/m ²	Surface

SUEWS describes the urban surface considering seven surface types (Figure 4):

1. paved surfaces (including roads, pavements, and other open impervious ground)
2. buildings
3. evergreen trees and shrubs
4. deciduous trees and shrubs
5. grass
6. bare soil
7. open water

Figure 4: The seven surface types considered in SUEWS (Source: <https://suews.readthedocs.io>)

To run the simulations, the plan area fraction of each surface type per grid cell is needed. This is computed for the urban core case studies of DISTENDER (Guimarães, Portugal and Metropolitan City of Turin, Italy) at 100, 500 m spatial resolution using multiple geospatial datasets from Copernicus that are reprojected and aligned to the same grid (Table 2).

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Table 2: Datasets employed for the computation of key urban morphological parameters in SUEWS simulations.

Dataset	Reference year	Source
CORINE Land Cover	2018	Copernicus
JRC-GEOSTAT Population	2018	European Commission
Tree cover density	2018	Copernicus
Dominant leaf type	2018	Copernicus
Grassland	2018	Copernicus
Water & Wetness	2018	Copernicus
Street tree layer	2018	Copernicus
GHS building height	2018	European Commission
European Settlement Map	2015	Copernicus
Global Forest Canopy Height	2019	University of Maryland

Namely, these datasets include:

- the CORINE Land Cover dataset (<https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>)
- the European Settlement Map dataset (<https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/GHSL/european-settlement-map>)
- the Grassland dataset (<https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/grassland/>)
- the Street Tree Layer dataset (<https://land.copernicus.eu/local/urban-atlas/street-tree-layer-stl-2018>)
- the Tree Cover Density dataset (<https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/forests/tree-cover-density>)
- the Dominant Leaf Type dataset (<https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/forests/dominant-leaf-type>)
- the Water & Wetness dataset (<https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/water-wetness>)

In addition, for every grid cell the height of buildings is determined from the Joint Research Centre (JRC) GHS-BUILT-H dataset (<https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset/ce7c0310-9d5e-4aeb-b99e-4755f6062557>), the height of trees from the Global Forest Canopy Height dataset (<https://glad.umd.edu/dataset/gedi>), and the population density from JRC-GEOSTAT dataset (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-data/population-distribution-demography/geostat>).

A summary of the main input variables for SUEWS is presented in the Annex 3.2.1.

2.2.4 Output Data

SUEWS output includes each term of the energy and water balance at every time-step. In addition, several diagnostic variables are computed inside the model, such as air temperature at 2 m and wind speed at 10 m. Furthermore, multiple further indicators will be calculated after simulations, such as heating and cooling degree days and heatwave metrics. For the latter, different heatwave definitions will be assessed such as the CTX90pct index (Perkins & Alexander, 2013) and the Excess Heat Factor (Nairn & Fawcett, 2015). The following is a brief summary of the computed indicators (as defined in the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and in Perkins & Alexander, 2013) using SUEWS output:

- Heatwave number: the number of heatwave events
- Heatwave frequency: the number of heatwave days
- Heatwave duration: the duration of the longest heatwave episode
- Heatwave mean duration: the average heatwave duration
- Heatwave magnitude: the mean magnitude of heatwaves
- Heatwave amplitude: the maximum magnitude of heatwaves
- Cooling degree days: A measure of the departure of the mean daily temperature above a given standard (typically a base of 25 °C): one cooling degree-day is accumulated for each degree above the standard. It provides an estimate of the energy demand for cooling of buildings.
- Heating degree days: A measure of the departure of the mean daily temperature below a given standard (typically a base of 18 °C): one heating degree-day is accumulated for each degree below the standard. It provides an estimate of the energy demand for heating of buildings.
- Summer days: Days when maximum temperature exceeds 25 °C
- Tropical nights: Days when minimum temperature exceeds 20 °C
- Warm spell duration indicator: Number of days contributing to a warm period (where the period has to be at least 6 days long)
- Number of hot days and nights: Annual count of consecutive days where both maximum and minimum temperature are greater than their corresponding climatological 95th percentile

A summary of the main output variables from SUEWS (including post-processing indicators) is presented in the Annex3.2.2.

2.2.5 Limitations

As mentioned in Section 2.2.2, SUEWS can be applied to large domains of multiple grid cells; however, it does not explicitly consider advection (i.e., $Q_A = 0$). More specifically, the micro-scale (i.e., sub-grid-scale) advection is not resolved in the model, but rather embedded within the parameterizations of the individual terms (Järvi et al., 2011). On the other hand, the inter-grid advection is assumed to be negligible and it is taken into account through the meteorological forcing data (Järvi et al., 2014). Another limitation of SUEWS is related to the 3-D representation of the urban structure. As SUEWS is a land surface model, the impacts of building morphology and street-level processes are, by design, less explicit than those resolved in an urban canopy model. That is, SUEWS only considers the vertical exchanges of heat, radiation, and momentum between the surface and the atmosphere. The

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impact of urban geometry on aerodynamic roughness, emissivity and albedo is reduced to specific, prescribed parameter values for each tile of the grid cells (Nazarian et al., 2023).

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2.3 Health impact

2.3.1 Introduction

Air pollution and climate change are two of the most pressing global environmental issues of our time, with significant implications for human health. In fact, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that outdoor air pollution contributes to around 4.2 million premature deaths worldwide each year. Fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) are two of the most harmful air pollutants, with significant long-term health impacts.

Exposure to air pollutants such as PM_{2.5} and NO₂ has been linked to a range of adverse health outcomes, including respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. At the same time, rising temperatures and extreme weather events associated with climate change are also known to have negative health impacts, particularly in vulnerable populations. To address these issues, it is important to understand the health effects of both air pollution and heat-related factors and to estimate their impacts on populations. To estimate the health impacts of air pollution and heat-related factors, various health impact assessment methodologies have been developed, each with its own strengths and limitations. For example, the methodology used by the European Environment Agency (EEA) relies on concentration-response functions and morbidity and mortality indicators, while other approaches may use different exposure-response functions or focus on specific health outcomes.

Overall, the estimation of health effects due to air pollution and heat-related factors is a crucial area of research, as it can help inform policies and interventions aimed at reducing the negative health impacts of these environmental factors. By better understanding the health impacts of air pollution and heat-related factors, we can work towards creating healthier and more sustainable environments for everyone.

2.3.2 Model description

Long-term health impacts of PM_{2.5} and NO₂ exposures are estimated, following the methodology applied by the European Environment Agency (EEA) in their annual health assessments (Soares et al., 2019). According to EEA (2018), PM_{2.5} and NO₂ are the pollutants with the most serious health impacts and with the most robust scientific evidence. The morbidity and mortality indicators considered are listed in Table 3. The concentration-response functions (CRFs) are selected according to the up-to-date recommendations of WHO air quality guidelines (WHO, 2021). The health impact assessment can be performed in three major steps, namely: (i) population exposure assessment; (ii) health risk estimation; and (iii) uncertainty calculation. Figure 5 shows the health impact assessment scheme, with an example for PM_{2.5}, long-term exposure, all-cause (natural) mortality, using hypothetical concentration and population values.

Detailed information on the health impact assessment can be found in Coelho et al. (2022) and Soares et al. (2019). Additionally, other indicators will be estimated as mortality and morbidity health outcomes, such as: years of life lost (YLL), years lived in disability/disease (YLD) and disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). YLL is defined as the years of potential life loss due to premature death. It is an estimate of the average number of years that a person would have lived if the person would not have died prematurely. YLL are calculated as the number of deaths at each age multiplied by the standard life expectancy for each age. YLD

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represent the number of disease/disability cases in a period multiplied by the average duration of disease/disability and weighted by a disease/disability factor. DALYs sum years of life lost (YLL) due to premature mortality and years lived in disability/disease (YLD).

Table 3: Health indicators to be considered in DISTENDER.

Mortality	Morbidity
PM (annual mean), long-term:	
PM2.5 - Mortality, all-cause (natural), age 30+ years	PM10 - Prevalence of bronchitis in children, age 6–12 (or 6–18) years
PM2.5 - Mortality, cerebrovascular disease (includes stroke), ischaemic heart disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and trachea, bronchus and lung cancer, age 30+ years	PM10 - Incidence of chronic bronchitis in adults (age 18+ years)
PM10 - Postneonatal (age 1–12 months) infant mortality, all-cause	
NO ₂ (annual mean), long-term:	
Mortality, all (natural) causes, age 30+ years	Prevalence of bronchitis symptoms in asthmatic children aged 5–14 years
Daily temperature:	
Heat-related premature deaths for the warm season (1 April to 30 September)	

Heat-related effects are estimated following the methodology applied by Gosling et al. (2017). For each CCS domain, heat-related mortality will be estimated using a specific linear exposure–response function (ERF) derived from Baccini et al. (2008), which will describe the relationship between temperature and daily heat-related mortality in terms of relative risk (RR). This ERF will be applied to calculate the daily attributable fraction (AF) for the exposed population, which will be the fraction of the mortality burden attributable to the risk factor of temperature above the threshold temperature. The AF will then be multiplied by the baseline daily mortality rate and the exposed population to yield the absolute number of daily heat-related deaths. Mortality will be calculated only for the warm season (1 April to 30 September).

Population exposure assessment:

1a) Grid: the area for which the health risk assessment will be calculated consists of a 4 cells grid with 1.2x1.2 km² horizontal resolution.

1b) Concentration Map: the air quality modelling results, for cells 1 to 4, show PM_{2.5} annual concentrations that vary between 5 and 15 µg m⁻³, for the year under analysis.

1c) Population/Exposure: the population is distributed across the grid and the exposure is calculated. For example, in cell 1, 10000 inhabitants are exposed to 15 µg·m⁻³ of PM_{2.5}.

Health risk estimation:

2a) Baseline Concentration: the baseline concentration for PM_{2.5} is 0 µg m⁻³, meaning that, for instance, for grid 1 the effect of the whole range of 25 µg m⁻³ of PM_{2.5} will be estimated.

2b) Relative Risk: in the case of PM_{2.5}, the concentration-response function used for total (all-cause) mortality in people above 30 years of age implies a relative risk of 1.062 per 10 µg m⁻³. Thus, assuming linearity, an increase of 10 µg m⁻³ of PM_{2.5} is associated with a 6.2 % increase in total mortality in the total population considered.

2c) Mortality: the total mortality (incidence base) in the country for the year under analysis and the population over 30 years of age is 10 deaths per 1000 inhabitants, so the number of deaths per grid is as shown.

2d) Premature Deaths: the number of deaths attributed to exposure to PM_{2.5} in each cell is obtained from:

$$\text{Relative Risk (RR)} = \exp(\beta * \text{concentration} - \text{baseline concentration}) = \exp(0.00602 * \text{concentration} - 0)$$

For cell 1: 1.162281

$$\text{Population Attributable Fraction (PAF)} = (\text{RR}-1) / \text{RR}$$

For cell 1: 0.139623

$$\text{Premature Deaths (PD)} = \text{PAF} * \text{mortality} * \text{population}$$

For cell 1: 13.96 ≈ 14

Uncertainty calculation:

3) Uncertainty: the uncertainty range is calculated using the lower (1.040) and upper (1.083) limits of the relative risk of PM_{2.5}, instead of 1.062.

The total mortality is then expressed as 18 premature deaths, with a 95 % confidence interval between 12 and 24.

Figure 5: Health impact assessment scheme. Example for PM_{2.5}, long-term exposure, all-cause (natural) mortality (adapted from EEA, 2018).

2.3.3 Input Data

- Annual average concentrations by grid cell for PM_{2.5} and NO₂, from T5.1
- population data stratified by age and sex
- mortality rate due to all causes

A table of socio-economic model inputs can be found in Annex 3.3.1

2.3.4 Output Data

Maps of health impact indicators for each CCS domain:

- YLL (Years of Life Lost)

- YLD (healthy life lost due to disability)
- DALY (Disability-adjusted life years)
- Heat-related premature deaths for the warm season (1 April to 30 September)

A table of model outputs can be found in Annex 3.3.2.

2.3.5 Limitations

- Uncertainties in concentration-response functions: Although concentration-response functions (CRFs) have been selected according to up-to-date WHO air quality guidelines, there are still uncertainties and limitations associated with these functions. There may be differences in the CRFs used across different locations, which may affect the estimates of health impacts.
- Limited quality of data: The accuracy of the health impact estimates relies on the availability of accurate and up-to-date data on air quality and weather conditions.
- Simplifications in the models: The models used to estimate the health impacts of air pollution and heat-related effects involve certain simplifications and assumptions. For instance, the models do not account for the potential interactions between air pollution and temperature, or the potential variations in vulnerability to air pollution and heat-related effects across different populations. Mortality is just estimated for age 30+ years old.
- Use of a fixed threshold temperature: The methodology used to estimate the heat-related effects involves the use of a fixed threshold temperature, which may not be appropriate for all locations. In some areas, the threshold temperature may be lower or higher than the value used in the model.
- Limited consideration of other risk factors: The models used to estimate the health impacts of air pollution and heat-related effects do not account for the potential impact of other risk factors.

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2.4 Energy

2.4.1 Introduction

Climate change effects can induce impacts on the energy sector (Verwiebe, et al., 2021), however studies demonstrate that even moderate changes in socio-economic factors may have a bigger contribute to energy demand than any climate-factors (Ruth & Lin, 2006). The energy demand sensitivity is directly related to the weather conditions. Several studies have shown energy demand changes as a result of changes in the weather conditions. Nevertheless, the relation between the weather conditions variations and the change in energy demand is highly dependent on multiple factors, such as, regional climatic factors and socio-economic variables. Climate change might contribute to higher energy demand per capita in some regions, while demand in other regions might decrease caused by different balances of higher cooling and lower heating requirements (Ahmed, et al., 2012).

Figure 6: Relationship between electricity demand and temperature (Ahmed, 2012)

2.4.2 Model description

Based on the specific characteristics mentioned in the previous sub-section, the energy model that fulfils the objectives of DISTENDER is a regression-based model that assesses the impacts caused by climate change in the energy sector. This approach is sensitive to the multiple variables that affect the energy demand and is adapted to the geographical scale of each case study. Despite most of the energy demand studies are carried out on a national scale (e.g., Emekwe and Emodi, 2022; Li, 2019), there are some studies that support the geographical city scale as a relevant factor (Zheng, et al., 2020). Adapting the geographical scale to each case study also allows the model to be sensitive to the regional economic sectors, since energy demand has different behaviour in residential, commercial, industry, agriculture and transportation sub-sectors. The model is calibrated with time series analysis, with the intention to forecast the effect of different climate and socio-economic scenarios on energy consumption and its impacts.

To implement the methodology and estimate climate-impacts on regional energy demand, a three-step modelling and estimation procedure was followed. Firstly, region-specific

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heating and cooling degree-days (HDD and CDD, respectively) were identified. Secondly, the time-series data of heating and cooling degree-days was used, together with energy prices, Gross Demand Product (GDP), population and energy consumption variables, in a fixed-effects regression model, to quantify the sensitivity of end use energy consumption by the residential, industry, transportation, agricultural and commercial sectors.

The energy demand data used in the methodology comprises both the demands per sector (industry, residential, commercial, agricultural and transportation) as well as the demands by type of energy (electricity, natural gas and oil products). The data was collected from the official sources (official national energy entities in each country) and considered according to the best data available. Whenever available, it was considered data for the period between 1979 and 2022 for the calibration and validation of the model. With the validation coefficient for each independent variable, we can estimate the energy impacts for each of the climate models and future climate scenarios.

The third and final step of the methodology is the geographical representation of the results. The energy system and, therefore, its impacts are normally not expressed geographically (Bednar, et al., 2017). When translated to spatial outputs, energy is normally expressed in administrative boundaries because the demand is more dependent on the sector type than the physical aspect (e.g., some types of industry need more energy, independently of the size of the buildings). Nevertheless, this study is focused on the expression of energy consumption per land use type. We linked the energy demand sectors to land use classification to represent geographically the impacts, needed to link to other project models.

2.4.3 Model inputs

The energy model uses different input variables which include socio-economic and meteorological parameters. The socio-economic variables considered are the population, GDP and energy price. Both population and GDP were collected for a national or regional scale according to the case study. The energy price was collected for the different sectors and type of energy, as mentioned above. For the meteorological variables, CDD and HDD, which are commonly used metrics in the energy sector, were calculated. These parameters were determined for each case study, based on daily maximum and minimum 2-meter air temperature.

A table of socio-economic model inputs can be found in Annex 3.4.1.

2.4.4 Model outputs

The main output from the energy model is the annual energy consumption for the different sectors and type of energy, in a national or regional scale depending on the specific case study.

Table 4: Output variables and metrics from the energy model.

Variable	Units	Temporal resolution
Energy consumption, per sector and type of energy	PJ	Annual

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A full list of model outputs can be found in Annex 3.4.2.

2.4.5 Limitations

The use and interpretation of this energy model can be affected by some limitations that need to be considered in the results:

- Temporal resolution: energy consumption input data is commonly only accessible with coarse temporal resolution, frequently yearly (depending on the spatial scale). Therefore, outputs are limited to the input data temporal resolution as well.
- Temporal calibration: when input data is only available yearly, so the model calibration is affected.
- Spatial expression: the energy consumption is difficult to express geographically with precision. The energy consumption is more accurately expressed by the type of sectors than land cover, for example, a small industry facility can consume more energy than an entire city, depending on the type of industrial processes in use.
- Political & socio-economic drivers' impact: energy use can be directly affected by policies and market regulations, with immediate expression in consumption. Therefore, weakening the prospective analysis of energy consumption.
- Data availability: the unavailability of data for some case studies during some or all years may affect the modelling of the energy consumption for specific combinations of sectors and energy types.

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2.5 Water: Floods/Droughts

2.5.1 Introduction

Climate change will significantly affect the hydrological cycle with all its components from precipitation, to soil water content, plant water demand and evapotranspiration, groundwater resources and runoff. Particularly the increasing frequency of extreme events such as floods and droughts are of major concern. While droughts build up over time and typically affect large areas, floods are often a spatially limited and fast event. Thus, the assessment of hydrological impacts of climate change and the associated adaptation and mitigation measures act on a large range of spatial and temporal scales, from local effects of flooding to continental effects of droughts, from short-term events of surface flow from convective cells to long-term effects of groundwater level changes or droughts. To address these different temporal and spatial scales as well as the different process dynamics the main focus is on assessing the effects of climate change and socio-economic measures upon the main water balance components. The actual state of water fluxes and water resources at a given location is in many areas very strongly affected by human management. While the natural system response is based on physical equations and its local parameterization and thereby to a large extent predictable, water management follows a set of rules, which depends upon the specific actors and their management goals. Thus, particularly in areas which are dominated by water transfer and pumping such as the Netherlands, the actual water fluxes at the surface are not necessarily defined primarily by physical drivers. Nevertheless, water balance studies assessing temporal and spatial differences of precipitation, evapotranspiration, runoff and change of water stored in surface and groundwater can be modelled. To address the complexity of different hydrological processes and the need for data by the decision-makers ranging from general information about changes in the water availability (e.g. on the sub-watershed scale) to local information, we utilized two different models: a) the semi-distributed, process based SWAT model to assess changes of the main water balance components and b) the raster-based process based MIKE model family to facilitate a more complex assessment of changes in the water balance components. While SWAT represents a robust and generally applicable hydrological model, the MIKE model family provides a sophisticated representation of processes in the watersheds which requires more information and expertise. Both models are described in the following sections.

2.5.2 Overview of the SWAT Model

The frequency and magnitude of hydro-climatic extremes, such as droughts and floods, increase in many regions worldwide due to climate change and could lead to severe socio-economic, structural and environmental impacts (Giorgi et al., 2018; Raikes et al., 2019). Quantification of hydro-climatic extremes helps in understanding the current status and potential risks of water-related disasters. In order to carry out regional long-term risk assessment, integrated water resources management (IWRM) and strategic planning is needed to be better prepared for future climate shocks (floods and droughts), long-term forecasts of climate change effects on extreme precipitation and flood frequencies with lead times of several decades. Eingrüber and Korres (2022) show the effects of different climate scenarios on water fluxes for a mesoscale watershed in Germany. For better decision making, a combination of climatological, ecohydrological and river systems models are indispensable tools in understanding the interaction of hydrological processes and

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environmental issues. They can be used to simulate changes in the magnitude and frequency of these extreme events. Accurate simulation of key water balance components, especially of runoff, evapotranspiration and soil water are crucial for water management and watershed development. To accomplish this within the framework of DISTENDER and for robust modelling of the impact of different climate and socio-economic scenarios upon water fluxes and water resources, the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT model) is used to simulate water fluxes at the land surface. SWAT is particularly suitable to model water fluxes of mesoscale watersheds under climate change. The software is freely available. It is a process-based model, well tested and can be used with generally available data. It also addresses key processes and controls of the water cycle namely: infiltration, soil water fluxes, groundwater recharge, evapotranspiration, runoff, nutrients/pesticides, erosion, land use/plant, management practices, channel processes, and many more.

2.5.3 Model description of the SWAT model

2.5.3.1 Purpose

SWAT is a continuous time, semi-distributed, watershed scale eco-hydrological model. It is developed by the USDA Agricultural Research Service to predict the impact of land management practices on water, sediment and agricultural chemical yields in large complex watersheds with varying soils, land use and management conditions over long periods of time (Arnold et al., 2012).

2.5.3.2 SWAT applications and development history

SWAT is one of the most comprehensive and widely used eco-hydrological models. It has been tested and applied extensively worldwide during the past years (Krysanova and Arnold, 2008; Arnold and Fohrer, 2005; Gassman et al., 2007, Akoko et al., 2021). Around 5795 studies¹ were published in various peer-reviewed scientific journals between 2000 and 2023 tackling different scientific issues and listed in the SWAT website², which is supported by the Centre for Agricultural and Rural Development (CARD). In addition, the model has been widely used for projecting the impacts of future hydro-climatic changes. For example, SWAT has been extensively used in Europe to quantify the impacts of climate change in different watersheds within the framework of projects supported by various European Commission (EC) agencies (Gassman et al., 2007). Table 6 provides an overview of major application categories of SWAT studies reported in the literature and includes studies describing applications of SWAT and other related models like ESWAT, SWAT-G, SWIM.

According to Arnold et al., (2012), the first version of SWAT was developed in the early 1990s and since then, it has been undergoing constant updates. The latest version of the model is called (SWAT+) which is a completely revised version of SWAT model and it features several improvements compared with previous versions, for example, the definition of landscape units that allow for a better representation of spatio-temporal dynamics and processes within a watershed.

¹ Includes studies describing applications of SWAT and other related modified models such as ESWAT, SWAT-G, SWIM, R-SWAT & SWAT, SWAT+..etc.

² https://www.card.iastate.edu/swat_articles/

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Table 5: Overview of major application categories of SWAT studies reported in the literature.

Primary application category	Hydrology only	Pollutant only	Hydrology and pollutant
Calibration and/or sensitivity analysis	15	2	20
Climate change impacts	22	---	8
GIS interface descriptions	3	2	3
Hydrologic assessments	42	---	---
Variation in configuration or data input effects	21	---	15
Comparisons with other models or techniques	5	1	7
Interfaces with other models	13	6	15
Pollutant assessments	---	6	57

Source: Adapted after Gassman et al., (2007)

2.5.3.3 Temporal and spatial resolution

SWAT is a deterministic, continuous time model that operates on a daily time step and is intended as a long-term impact model that runs for many years (typically 10-30 years). However, it is not intended for detailed modelling of single-event storm simulation, flood routing or water level simulations (Arnold et al., 1998).

In terms of spatial resolution, SWAT can be used in different spatial scales such as Watershed/Basin, Landscape units, and Hydrologic Response Unit (HRU). Using HRUs as elementary process units builds upon the deterministic paradigm that identical landscape elements result in identical hydrological reaction upon the same input (here meteorological data, esp. precipitation, temperature, humidity). Hydrological fluxes at the land surface are determined by temporally invariable parameters such as topography and soil properties as well as by . Thus, HRUs are defined from unique combinations these three land surface elements. HRUs exist within sub-watersheds. Within a sub-watershed, the meteorological divers are assumed to be identical. This spatial modelling concept strongly reduces the computational load, it maintains the physical and deterministic base of the model and facilitates assessment of different scenarios. SWAT uses a two-level spatial representation scheme: i) watershed are identified based on topographic analysis and ii) sub-watersheds are defined from river confluence or gauge locations.

Flux are calculated on HRUs. HRUs are not explicitly geo-located within a sub-watershed. Runoff from HRUs drains into streams, sub-watersheds are connected by streams. SWAT simulates water fluxes within each HRU addressing processes such as plant growth, energy balance, soil evaporation and plant transpiration, water body evaporation, snow pack and snow melt, runoff generation and infiltration using the following daily water balance equation and using soil water as a key water storage (Neitsch et al., 2011):

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$$SW_t = SW_0 + R_{\text{day}} - Q_{\text{surf}} - E_a - w_{\text{seep}} - Q_{\text{gw}} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

where SW_t is the soil water content (mm), SW_0 is the initial soil water content (mm), t is the time (days), R_{day} is the precipitation (mm/d), Q_{surf} is the surface runoff (mm/d), E_a is the evapotranspiration on day i (mm/d), w_{seep} is the water entering the vadose zone from the soil profile (mm/d), and Q_{gw} is the return flow (subsurface flow) (mm/d).

The water balance equation governs all the hydrological processes in SWAT. Detailed description of all hydrological processes in SWAT are given in the SWAT theoretical documentation (<https://swat.tamu.edu/docs/>) and are illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Hydrology component in SWAT. Source: (Neitsch et al., 2011)

2.5.4 Model input data to SWAT

In order for SWAT to simulate runoff and other processes in the catchment, it requires climatic data, topographic information represented by a digital elevation model (DEM) or digital surface model (DSM), soil data, and land use data. Climatic inputs used in SWAT include daily precipitation, maximum and minimum temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed, which can be input from measured records and/or generated, or downloaded from public domain data-source. Observed data such as discharge, sediment, and water quality variables (N, P) will also be needed for model calibration and validation procedure depending on the intended output and the model purpose. Most of these data are available in public domain data sources or could be acquired from regional or national related agencies. A summary of model inputs that are used in modelling the selected watersheds in the DISTENDER project and their sources is given in Table 7. In addition, it provides examples of other public domain data-sources from where the required data can be downloaded.

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Table 6: An overview of SWAT model input data and examples of public domain data-sources

Data type	Source	Other potential sources
Digital Elevation Model (DEM)	ALOS World 3D DSM - 30m	SRTM- CSI-CGIAR USGS Earth Explorer
Land use	CORINE Land Cover dataset 2018	Golbcover Copernicus Global Land service
Soil map	Soil Map of the World (FAO/UNESCO soil map)	Harmonized World Soil Database ISRAC soil grid
Weather data (P, T, ET, Wind speed...etc)	European reanalysis data (ERA 5 land) (ECMWF). Observed data provided by WP9, Simulations and downscaling products data provided by WP 4	NOAA) / ERA5 NCEP / CFSR National weather service
Streamflow for calibration	Provided by the case studies	The Global Runoff Data Centre (GRDC) INSPIRE
Climate change projections	4 downscaled (local) climate scenarios	HadCM3, MPI-RCSM, DMI-HIRHAM5, SMHI-RCA4
Reservoirs and management	Literature/ partially provided by the case studies, input from WP6	Different local and regional institutions

A full list of socio-economic model inputs can be found in Annex 3.5.1.

2.5.5 Model outputs of SWAT

Example of potential model outputs that will be generated at different spatial scales are:

a) At the watershed scale:

- Summary indicators for mean system behaviour change and for the whole watershed (see Figure 8).
- Monthly or annual sums of water fluxes and storages.
- Changes in water fluxes for different meteorological scenarios or land use scenarios (e.g. surface runoff, ET, etc...)

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Figure 8: Example of percentage changes in different water fluxes in the whole watershed of a scenario versus a baseline.

b) At the sub-watershed scale (see Figure 9):

- water balance components in each subbasin (P, ET, runoff)
- Post processing and presentation of model outputs for (sub-)watersheds (e.g. box-whiskers-diagram, expressed either as percentage change or relative change relative to validation period or as absolute values)
- Aggregated hydrological variables such as average annual values (for surface runoff, ET, infiltration to groundwater).

Figure 9: Example output for sub-watersheds indicating change in evapotranspiration (ET) per sub-basin and changed cropland and urban area as percentage of sub-basin area between 1989/90 and 2009/10. (Wagner et al., 2013)

- c) At the HRU Scale: water balance components each HRU.
- d) At the reach / stream scale for selected locations:

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- Time series of hydrological flux components for sub-watersheds: surface runoff (see Figure 10), ET, infiltration, baseflow, lateral flow).
- Hydrological storages: relative changes in soil water content, reservoir content (If all required reservoir parameters and management information are provided).

Figure 10: Example of average daily runoff values (m^3/s) for specific scenario

In addition, the model results can be aggregated and presented in terms of intensity, frequency:

- Recurrence rates as intensity -Frequency graphs- and duration curves of low and high flows for selected runoff gauges.
- Hydrological main values and standards statistics indices (Low and high flow index: Q95/Q50 and Q10/Q50).

A full list of model outputs can be found in Annex 3.5.2.

2.5.6 Expected limitations and model uncertainties of SWAT

The accuracy and type of the outputs to be generated are subject to some limitations in terms of:

- Spatial resolution: no grid data; smallest spatially geo-located area: sub-watershed, smallest spatial entity (not geo-located within a sub-watershed: Hydrological Response Unit. Thus, only one meteorological input data time-series per sub-watershed is used.
- Availability of good quality runoff data for model calibration and validation (with good overlapping span from different gauging stations) is often limited.
- Availability of reservoir parameterization data and management data (operation rules) is limited. Reservoir operation for hydropower and other uses can be modelled in SWAT using general management plans.
- spatial extent: SWAT simulates fluxes and storages in watersheds. Thus, as case studies are represented by a rectangular grid, not the full study area for some case

studies is covered and on the other hand the model domain may exceed the CCS domain.

- modelling of soil water fluxes and storage strongly depends of soil parameterization. Detailed information on soil parameters is often lacking.
- SWAT cannot model water allocation for different water users in the catchment and cannot quantify the groundwater volume.
- For watersheds which are dominated by human management (e.g. pumping in the Netherlands) surface runoff measurements cannot be used for calibration and validation of the model.

2.5.7 Model description of the MIKE model

The MIKE SHE (Systeame Hydrologique European) and MIKE HYDRO models are used to simulate surface runoff of selected mesoscale watersheds under climate change context. These models cover many components: climate, hydrology, erosion, land use/vegetation, management practices, channel and river routing, dam and reservoir effect, and water bodies.

2.5.7.1 Purpose

MIKE SHE is a modelling system that describes the flow of water and solutes in a catchment in a distributed, physically-based way. It covers the major processes in the hydrologic cycle and includes process models for evapotranspiration, overland flow, unsaturated flow, groundwater flow, and channel flow and their interactions (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Hydrologic processes simulated by MIKE SHE

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Each of these processes can be represented at different levels of spatial distribution and complexity, according to the goals of the modelling study, the availability of field data and the modeller's choices, (Butts et al. 2004). MIKE SHE is fully physically based. Thus, each hydrological process is modelled by a set of physical equations describing mass flow and momentum transfer, such as the Darcy equation for saturated flow in porous media, or the Richards equation for unsaturated flow. It is also fully distributed: the governing equations were solved using finite-difference approaches based on a gridded spatial discretization common to all processes (Graham & Butts 2005; Refsgaard et al. 2010). This implies numerical solutions of the coupled partial differential equations for overland (2D) and channel flow (1D), unsaturated flow (1D) and saturated flow (3D) together with a description of evapotranspiration and snowmelt processes.

Figure 12 depicts the key processes simulated by MIKE SHE. Further details are provided in Abbott et al., 1986 and Refsgaard and Storm, 1995. MIKE SHE uses MIKE HYDRO to simulate channel flow. It includes comprehensive facilities for modelling complex channel networks, lakes and reservoirs, and river structures, such as gates, sluices, and weirs. In highly managed river systems, accurate representation of the river structures and their operation rules is essential. The model data are specified in a variety of formats independent of the model domains and grids, including native GIS formats. At run time, the spatial data is mapped onto the numerical grid, which makes it easy to change the spatial discretization (DHI, 2023).

Figure 12: Schematic view of the processes in MIKE SHE. Arrows show the exchange pathways for water between the process models

2.5.7.2 Temporal and spatial resolution

The temporal and spatial resolution of MIKE SHE can vary depending on the model setup and the specific application. In general, MIKE SHE can be used to simulate catchment-scale hydrological processes with a spatial resolution of a few meters to kilometres and a temporal resolution of minutes to hours. However, the specific resolution used in a given application will depend on the specific modelling objectives and available data (DHI, 2023). MIKE SHE allows users to set the time step to suit the needs of their specific application. Generally, the time step can range from minutes to hours, depending on the complexity of the model and the availability of data. The spatial resolution of MIKE SHE refers to the size of the grid cells or computational elements used to divide the catchment. The size of the grid cells can vary depending on the level of detail required for the simulation. Typically, grid cell sizes range

from a few meters to kilometres, depending on the scale of the catchment and the resolution of the input data. The resolution of input data, such as topography, soil properties, land use, and meteorological data, can also affect the spatial resolution of the model. In the DISTENDER project, we will use a temporal resolution for different catchments between 1 and 2 hours, and the spatial resolution between 200 meters for small catchments and 1 km for large catchments.

2.5.7.3 Model input data and parameters

The input data required to run MIKE are identical to the SWAT model. However, additional data may be needed particularly for calibration. Not all parameters are available in all watersheds. This may limit the application of MIKE so selected watersheds or selected events. Table 8 provides an overview about the key parameters used to calibrate the MIKE SHE (DHI, 2023).

Table 7: Principle parameters for MIKE SHE

Module	Principle Parameters	Calibration Parameters	Other Parameters
Overland flow (finite difference)	Surface roughness		Detention storage
Overland flow (sub catchment-based)	Surface roughness		Detention storage Slope parameters
River flow	River bed roughness leakage coefficient		
Unsaturated flow (finite difference)	Saturated hydraulic conductivity		Soil water contents at saturation, field capacity, and wilting point
Unsaturated flow (2-layer method)	Saturated hydraulic conductivity		Soil water contents at saturation, field capacity, and wilting point Capillary thickness
Actual Evapotranspiration	Leaf Area Index Root depth		Canopy Interception FAO Crop coefficient Kristensen and Jensen ET parameters
Groundwater flow (finite difference)	Hydraulic conductivity Specific yield Specific storage		Drain level Drain time constants

2.5.7.4 Model outputs

MIKE SHE produces a range of outputs that can be used to analyse the hydrological processes occurring in a catchment. The specific outputs produced depend on the parameters and settings used in the model, as well as on the level of detail and complexity of the model. Some common outputs of MIKE SHE include:

- **Water Balance:** MIKE SHE can calculate the water balance for a catchment by tracking the inputs and outputs of water. The model can estimate the amount of water

that is stored in the soil, infiltrates into the groundwater, evaporates from the surface, and flows into streams and rivers.

- **Streamflow:** MIKE SHE can simulate streamflow at various locations throughout the catchment. The model can estimate the timing and magnitude of peak flows, low flows, and the overall discharge of the stream.
- **Groundwater Flow:** MIKE SHE can simulate groundwater flow and the movement of solutes through the subsurface.
- **Soil Moisture:** MIKE SHE can simulate the moisture content of the soil at various depths. The model can estimate the availability of water for plants and the likelihood of soil saturation or drought conditions.
- **Evapotranspiration:** MIKE SHE can estimate the rate of evapotranspiration from the land surface. The model can calculate the amount of water that is lost to the atmosphere through both plant transpiration and evaporation from the soil surface.
- **Floods and Droughts:** MIKE SHE can simulate the response of the catchment to extreme weather events, such as floods and droughts. The model can estimate the likelihood and severity of these events and help in designing effective management strategies.

These outputs can be visualized as maps, graphs, or time series data, allowing users to analyse the hydrological processes occurring in the catchment and identify areas for potential improvement or intervention. The following table summarizes the hydrological parameters and water balance components.

Table 8: Output hydrological parameters used for the current study

Hydrological parameter	Data type	Unit	Notes
Actual evapotranspiration	Evapotranspiration rate	mm/day	Evapotranspiration occurring under actual soil moisture conditions in the period under study for the given climate
Actual transpiration	Evapotranspiration rate	mm/day	Evaporation of water occurs mainly through the pores of the leaves.
Actual soil evaporation	Evapotranspiration rate	mm/day	Actual soil evaporation depends on factors such as soil properties, land use, and vegetation.
Depth of overland water	Water depth	m	Represents the actual amount of water on the surface
Overland flow in the x direction	Discharge	M3/sec	Runoff on a slope has a positive x-direction
Overland flow in y direction	Discharge	M3/sec	Runoff on a slope has a positive y-direction
Infiltration to unsaturated zone (UZ)	Infiltration	mm/day	Water movement toward the system is positive
River Discharge	Discharge	m ³ /sec	
Average water content in the root zone	Water content	Vol %	

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2.5.7.5 Expected limitations

MIKE SHE, in its original formulation, can be characterized as a deterministic, physics-based, distributed model code. It was developed as a fully integrated alternative to the more traditional lumped, conceptual rainfall-runoff models. A physics-based code solves the partial differential equations describing mass flow and momentum transfer, and the parameters in these equations can be obtained from measurements and used in the model. For example, the St. Venant equations (open channel flow) and the Darcy equation (saturated flow in porous media) are physics-based equations (DHI,2023).

Although there are no physical limits to the size of a model, there are practical and hardware limits. The practical limits are generally related to run time. More detailed modelling (e.g. slightly smaller grid size) can quickly lead to longer run times. Further limitations are (DHI,2023):

- the significant amount of data required, and the cost of data acquisition;
- the complexity of the physics-based solution requires substantial execution time;
- the complexity may lead to over-parameterized descriptions;
- a physics-based model attempts to represent flow processes at the grid scale with mathematical descriptions that are derived for small scale experimental conditions.

Therefore, it is often practical to use simplified process descriptions. In the simplest case, MIKE SHE can use fully distributed conceptual approaches to model the watershed processes. For advanced applications, MIKE SHE can simulate all the processes using physics-based methods.

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2.6 AFOLU models

2.6.1 Introduction

Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use (AFOLU) systems can be viewed as highly complex systems in which a number of management practices determine the development of crops, trees, shrubs, pasture, and/or livestock. This makes it difficult to determine the impact of specific management decisions on farm profitability. To address this complexity, bio-economic modelling can contribute to a better understanding of the trade-offs related to managerial decisions.

Within the AFOLU sector, key factors that can be considered as determinants of adoption of recommended practices are their profitability relative to alternative enterprises and their feasibility, in terms of the use of farm resources (Burgess et al., 2000; Graves et al., 2005). In order to estimate the profitability and feasibility of agricultural, forestry and agroforestry systems under different Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs) modelling becomes essential. Compared to agricultural models, AFOLU models have the advantage of being able to simulate the growth of a variety of systems such as agricultural, forestry and agroforestry. For example, while studies such as Moreno and Pulido (2009) and López-Díaz et al. (2015) indicate that increased tree cover has the potential to improve pasture production and profitability, by using agricultural models it is difficult to determine the effect of the tree in monetary terms or to identify the tree cover density that maximizes economic profitability. In recent years, various biophysical models such as Hi-sAFe (Dupraz et al. 2004), SCUAF (Young et al. 1998), WaNuLCAS (van Noordwijk and Lusiana 1999), and Yield-SAFE (Van der Werf et al. 2007) have been developed to simulate the growth and interaction of trees and crops in silvoarable systems. Some economic models have also been developed to assess the financial profitability of silvoarable systems. These for example, include POPMOD (Thomas 1991), ARBUSTRA (Liagre 1997), and Farm-SAFE (Graves et al. 2011).

During the SAFE project, the Yield-SAFE model (Van der Werf et al. 2007) was developed to simulate the yields of crops and trees in agricultural, agroforestry, and forestry systems. During the AGFORWARD project, Yield-SAFE was adapted to quantify environmental externalities of arable, silvoarable and forestry systems.

2.6.2 Model description

The Yield-SAFE model is a daily-time-step model and simulates the yields of crops and trees in agricultural, agroforestry, and forestry systems (van der Werf et al., 2007). The overall objective of the model is to analyse the dynamics of competitive resource acquisition and the associated growth of the constituent components in an agroforestry stand with the minimum number of equations. Such an equation- and parameter-sparse approach is chosen because it provides the best chance that robust parameter values can be identified from experiments. Dynamic equations for the following state variables were identified as essential:

- (1) biomass of tree;
- (2) leaf area of tree;
- (3) number of shoots of tree;
- (4) biomass of crop;

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- (5) leaf area of crop;
- (6) heat sum;
- (7) available soil water.

Biomasses of trees and crops are used to derive temporally integrated timber volumes and crop yields. Leaf area of trees and crops are essential because they govern radiation capture, and thus the capacity for dry matter production and the associated water loss through transpiration. The number of shoots per tree is required because it governs the potential leaf area within a given year. By contrast the intra-annual leaf area dynamics (at the time scale of days to months) are primarily governed by the growth of leaf area per shoot. Available soil water is included to account for differential growth conditions across Europe with respect to the degree of water limitation, due to variation in precipitation, soil depth and water holding properties of soils. Finally, a heat sum is integrated each season to define phenological development of the crops. Nutrient dynamics are not included, because of lack of information from existing agroforestry trials necessary to determine pertinent parameters. The model can be readily extended to include nutrient dynamics, e.g. by quantifying the minimum nutrient uptake required to produce calculated water-limited yields (cf. Van Keulen and Wolf, 1986).

Yield-SAFE was developed under the EU SAFE project (Dupraz et al., 2005). Within the AGFORWARD project (see Palma et al., 2016), the model was enhanced to more accurately predict the delivery of ecosystem services provided by agroforestry systems relative to forestry and arable systems. The model has been successfully applied in numerous contexts and case studies (e.g., Giannitsopoulos et al., 2020; Crous-Duran et al., 2020; 2019; García de Jalón et al., 2018; Palma et al., 2018). For more information about the description of the model and its parameters see van der Werf et al. (2007).

Carbon sequestration

Estimates for carbon sequestration in above-ground biomass can be obtained from the Yield-SAFE model. García de Jalón et al. (2018) and Kaske et al. (2021) show an application in a case study with poplar plantations. It is assumed that timber for long-term utilisation (e.g. timber used in construction work, such as timber framed buildings) can be assigned to carbon stocks. In this way, only standing timber should be considered and firewood biomass with short-term utilisation should be excluded from the analysis. The following three steps can be followed to obtain carbon stock estimates typically given per tonne CO₂ equivalent:

1. Conversion of fresh timber volume into dry timber mass. Since the Yield-SAFE model provides timber volume predictions, this needs to be converted into a timber mass. This is done using a wood density value for specific tree species.
2. Conversion of dry timber mass into timber carbon. This is done assuming values from Nair et al. (2009) and Nair (2011) showing that 50% of the mass of timber is carbon.
3. Conversion of carbon into CO₂e is done by scaling the molecular mass of carbon dioxide (44 g mol⁻¹) to the atomic mass of carbon (12 g mol⁻¹) in tree biomass. Thus, 1 kg of carbon taken up into biomass is equivalent to an emission of 3.67 kg CO₂e.

The following Equation can be used to convert the simulated biomass into carbon dioxide equivalent sequestration (t CO₂e ha⁻¹ y⁻¹):

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$$Seq. CO_2e_t = 0.50 \times \beta_{timber} \times \frac{Atomic\ weight\ CO_2}{Atomic\ weight\ C} \quad Eq.2$$

where $Seq. CO_2e_t$ is the sequestered carbon dioxide equivalent ($t CO_2e ha^{-1} y^{-1}$) in time t , where 0.50 is assumed to be the carbon content of dry timber (Nair 2011), β_{timber} is the annual increment in timber mass on a dry weight basis, and the final component converts carbon to a carbon dioxide equivalent.

2.6.3 Input Data

The main model inputs of Yield-SAFE are climate and soil variables. As the Yield-SAFE model will be run for every cell in a gridded map, a crucial model input variable is a land use map. This determines, which specific crop or plantation will be simulated in each cell of the gridded map.

Important model inputs that may play a key role in the context of scenarios and strategies are changes in land use. These include changes in population increase, density and urban sprawling that may lead to changes such as from agricultural and forest land to urban land. Changes in societal demands for the environment such as increasing demands for introducing more trees on arable land can play an important role in driving land use changes within the AFOLU sector. In addition to this, changes in costs and prices are also relevant. For instance, whilst increases in some costs could lead to less intensive land use or even to agricultural abandonment, changes in commodity prices could lead to changes in farmers' preferences for specific crop types. EU policies such as Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), through subsidies, can have significant influence in determining land use changes. The following table shows the main input data of the Yield-SAFE model.

Table 9: Main input data of the Yield-SAFE model

Biophysical Model	Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution (if applicable)	Temporal resolution (if applicable)
Yield-SAFE	Current cover	ha	Gridded, case study area	None
Yield-SAFE	Future cover	ha	Gridded, case study area	None
Yield-SAFE	Farm management operations parameters	NA	Gridded, case study area	None
Yield-SAFE	Mean air temperature	C	Gridded, case study area	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Precipitation	mm	Gridded, case study area	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Solar Radiation	MJ m ⁻²	Gridded, case study area	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Wind velocity	m s ⁻¹	Gridded, case study area	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Mean relative humidity	%	Gridded, case study area	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Soil depth	mm	Gridded, case study area	None
Yield-SAFE	Soil texture (percent clay)	%	Gridded, case study area	None
Yield-SAFE	Soil texture (percent silt)	%	Gridded, case study area	None
Yield-SAFE	Soil texture (percent sand)	%	Gridded, case study area	None

For the sake of completeness, socio-economic model inputs are also listed in Annex 3.6.1.

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2.6.4 Output Data

The main output of the Yield-SAFE model will be annual yields ($\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) for each cell in a gridded map. A gridded map for each CCS and year will be produced. Main outputs that are expected to show significant effects due to the socio-economic and climatic changes will be changes in yields in agricultural, forest and agroforestry systems. Some strategies (interventions/measures) that could be implemented in the model are land use changes (e.g. from agriculture to forest, agriculture to urban), changes in crop types (e.g. from wheat to maize), introducing trees in arable lands as a result of addressing EU objectives of increasing tree cover in arable and pasture land, introducing crop-types more resilient to weather extremes (e.g. droughts) and changes in sowing dates as adaptation strategies. The results of the adoption of the strategies can be shown in physical units ($\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) or through relative changes in yields (e.g. a decrease of 10 % in the yield of wheat) in the aforementioned gridded maps.

The following table shows the main output variables of the Yield-SAFE model.

Table 10: Main output data of the Yield-SAFE model

Model	Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution
Yield-SAFE	Yield (tree component)	kg/ha	Gridded, case study	Yearly
Yield-SAFE	Tree density (tree component)	(tree m^{-2})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Leaf development per shoot (tree component)	(m^2)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Leaf area per tree (tree component)	($\text{m}^2 \text{ tree}^{-1}$)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Leaf area index (tree component)	($\text{m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Fraction light interception (tree component)	(m^{-2})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Potential growth (tree component)	(g tree^{-1})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Water reduced growth (tree component)	(g tree^{-1})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Actual growth accounting for respiration when in leaf (tree component)	(g tree^{-1})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Biomass per tree (tree component)	(g tree^{-1})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Number of shoots per tree (tree component)	(tree^{-1})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Water uptake (tree component)	($\text{m}^3 \text{ tree}^{-1}$)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Volume of timber (tree component)	($\text{m}^3 \text{ tree}^{-1}$)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Height (tree component)	(m)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Diameter at breast height (tree component)	(cm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Pruned branchwood per tree (tree component)	(g tree^{-1})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Pruned branchwood (tree component)	($\text{m}^{-3} \text{ ha}^{-1}$)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Number of harvested trees (tree component)	(tree m^{-2})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Timber volume of stand (tree component)	($\text{m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Harvested timber (tree component)	(m ha^{-1})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Volume of branchwood (tree component)	(m ha^{-1})	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Harvested branchwood (tree component)	(m ha^{-1})	Gridded, case study	Daily

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Yield-SAFE	Clear stem height (tree component)	(m)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Canopy area (tree component)	(%)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Fruit yield increment (tree component)	(g tree ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Fruit yield (tree component)	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Tree timber biomass (tree component)	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Tree branch biomass (tree component)	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Total canopy biomass (tree component)	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Potential growth (crop component)	(g m ⁻² crop)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Actual growth (crop component)	(g m ⁻²)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Leaf area index (crop component)	(m ² m ⁻²)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Biomass (crop component)	(g m ⁻²)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Water uptake (crop component)	(m ³ m ⁻²)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Total dry weight per cropped area (crop component)	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Yield per cropped area (crop component)	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Yield 2 per cropped area (crop component)	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Total weight per total area (crop component)	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Yield per total area (crop component)	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Volumetric water content (crop component)	(mm mm ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	pF (soil water tension, defined as the log of the water potential in cm water)	log(cm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Potential evaporation	(mm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Actual evaporation	(mm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Flow to groundwater	(mm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Crop water uptake (crop component)	(mm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Tree water uptake (tree component)	(mm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Overhead irrigation application	(mm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Soil water deficit	(mm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Critical deficit irrigation (tree component)	(mm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Critical deficit irrigation (crop component)	(mm)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Root Biomass (tree component)	(g tree ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	Carbon Sequestration	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily
Yield-SAFE	CO ₂ Sequestration	(t ha ⁻¹)	Gridded, case study	Daily

2.6.5 Limitations

The Yield-SAFE model is subject to several limitations that should be taken into account when interpreting the results.

First of all, the model is very simple. Van der Werf et al. (2007) in support of the simplicity approach of the model, explained the following arguments: i) a simpler model is often easier

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to parameterise and may produce more robust results; ii) it is less work to build; and iii) it is easier to explain and understand. In addition, this model simplicity results in a shorter learning curve when the model is used in upscaling studies, and this may favour its inclusion in higher level studies, e.g. explorations of land use. As the authors stated, Yield-SAFE was built with the philosophy that it could be extended when simulation of realistic situations required further detailing.

Another limitation that should be taken into consideration is the lack of high-quality data for the model calibration in a regional modelling approach, i.e. the model run of every cell in a gridded map. When the model is used to simulate plant growth and yield in a determined plot, usually the model calibration is based on a number of available variables such as leaf area index in different times of the year obtained from experimental plots. This process should allow an adequate calibration in those cases. However, in a regional assessment the model needs to be run in every cell of a gridded map in a given geographical area. Ideally, in order to perform the model calibration with high accuracy, data for calibration such as daily leaf area index for each plant species should be available for several time-steps throughout time. As this data is not available in all cells of a gridded map, the model calibration is based on historical yields obtained from agricultural statistics and databases and the same value represents the entire geographical region (NUTS-2 or NUTS-3).

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3 Annex

This annex contains lists of model socio-economic inputs and model outputs of the biophysical impact models in WP5. Additional results are generated by the economic models in WP7 and by the model in WP3.

3.1 Emissions and air quality

3.1.1 Emissions and air quality: socio-economic inputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution
Population data	Number	CCS domains and resolutions; Data to be provided by WP3 can be by administrative region or at country level if no higher spatial detail is available	
Land use including residential areas, commercial areas, industrial areas	ha		
Fuel type consumption for residential use	ton		
Fuel type consumption for transports	ton		
Industrial activity/production/extension (to have an idea of changes in industry in the CCS in each scenario)	ton ha		
% of renewable energy production	%		
% of electrification for transport, residential and industrial sectors	%		
road network	km		
vehicle fleet composition	Number		
Waste production	ton		

3.1.2 Emissions and air quality outputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution if applicable	Temporal resolution
NO ₂ concentration	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	Case study	Hourly
O ₃ concentration	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	Case study	Hourly
PM ₁₀ concentration	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	Case study	Hourly
PM ₂₅ concentration	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	Case study	Hourly
Greenhouse gases emissions	t	Case study	annual

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3.2 Urban heat

3.2.1 Urban heat: socio-economic inputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution
Building fraction		100 m – 500 m	Yearly
Road fraction		100 m – 500 m	Yearly
Vegetation fraction		100 m – 500 m	Yearly
Population density		100 m – 500 m	Yearly

3.2.2 Urban heat outputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution	Comment
Air temperature at 2 m	°C	100 m – 500 m	Hourly	
Surface temperature	°C	100 m – 500 m	Hourly	
Relative humidity at 2m	%	100 m – 500 m	Hourly	
Average air temperature at 2m	°C	100 m – 500 m	Daily, monthly, yearly	Postprocessing
Maximum air temperature at 2m	°C	100 m – 500 m	Daily, monthly, yearly	Postprocessing
Minimum air temperature at 2m	°C	100 m – 500 m	Daily, monthly, yearly	Postprocessing
HWN, Heatwave number	–	100 m – 500 m	Seasonally, yearly	Postprocessing
HWF, Heatwave frequency	–	100 m – 500 m	Seasonally, yearly	Postprocessing
HWD, Heatwave duration	Days	100 m – 500 m	Seasonally, yearly	Postprocessing
HWDM, Heatwave duration mean	Days	100 m – 500 m	Seasonally, yearly	Postprocessing
HWM, Heatwave magnitude	°C	100 m – 500 m	Seasonally, yearly	Postprocessing

HWA, Heatwave amplitude	°C	100 m – 500 m	Seasonally, yearly	Postprocessing
Cooling degree days (CDD)	–	100 m – 500 m	Yearly	Postprocessing
Heating degree days (HDD)	–	100 m – 500 m	Yearly	Postprocessing
SU, Summer days	–	100 m – 500 m	Seasonally, yearly	Postprocessing
TR, Tropical nights	–	100 m – 500 m	Seasonally, yearly	Postprocessing
WSDI, Warm spell duration indicator	Days	100 m – 500 m	Seasonally, yearly	Postprocessing
TXdTNd, number of hot days and nights	–	100 m – 500 m	Seasonally, yearly	Postprocessing

3.3 Health impact

3.3.1 Health: socio-economic inputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution	Source	Comments
Population data by age groups		CCS domain and resolution	Annual	Scenario	
mortality rates by age groups		CCS domain and resolution	annual	Scenario	

3.3.2 Health outputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution	Comment
YLL - Years of Life Lost	years	Case study	annual	
PD1 - Premature deaths	number	Case study	annual	
PD2 - Premature deaths	number	Case study	annual	

3.4 Energy

3.4.1 Energy: socio-economic inputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution
Population	In thousands		Yearly
Gross Demand Product (GDP)	In million 2017 US\$		Yearly

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Energy price	US cents kWh ⁻¹ , excluding taxes		Yearly
Cooling Degree Days (CDD)	Degree days		Yearly
Heating Degree Days (HDD)	Degree days		Yearly

3.4.2 Energy outputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution	Comment
Energy consumption per source (demand)	PJ	As applicable: city, region, or country level	Yearly	By fuel type and sector (if applicable)
Economic model sector energy				
Total energy cost	€/kWh	As applicable: city, region, or country level	Yearly	By fuel type and sector (if applicable)
Energy savings	€/Year	As applicable: city, region, or country level	Yearly	Savings by measure and fuel type

3.5 Water: Floods/Droughts

The data in this section apply to the SWAT model

3.5.1 Water: socio-economic inputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution	Source	Comments
Agriculture management data, such as information on major crops with their planting and harvesting schedules, fertilization (N and P) and irrigation practices	Per land use class and HRU	Per land use class, HRU	Sub-annual	Agricultural model	Same as agricultural model
Future water demand, use (abstraction and water transfer) Agri, industry, domestic	10 ⁶ m ³ per time		Monthly to annual	Scenario	
Land use and land cover	-		Annual	Scenario	

Reservoirs operation	-		Up to daily	Scenario	Can be set to a minimum flow volume, the reservoir has to provide, if no data is available from case studies
Environmental flow requirements	10 ⁶ m ³ per time		daily	Scenario, or from Environmental Flow Requirement (EFR) in the selected country from the Global Environmental Flow Information System-GEFIS: http://eflows.wmi.org/	
Wetlands management	-			Scenario	Tendency/intensity Holding capacity, minimum water release

3.5.2 Water outputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution if applicable	Temporal resolution	Comment
water yield / runoff	mm or m ³ / d	(sub-) catchment	Daily	Results will be for catchments and sub-catchments, not on politically defined areas
surface runoff	mm or m ³ / d	(sub-) catchment	Daily	
evapotranspiration	mm or m ³ / d	(sub-) catchment	Daily	
soil water content	Vol%	(sub-) catchment	Daily	Differentiation of layers may (!) be possible.

Groundwater recharge	mm / d	(sub-) catchment	Daily	
Lateral flow	mm / d	(sub-) catchment	Daily	From soil into rivers, reservoirs, and onto the surface
surface flow	mm / d	(sub-) catchment	Daily	Into rivers, reservoirs, and on the surface
Groundwater flow	mm / d	(sub-) catchment	Daily	Into rivers, reservoirs, onto landscape
Reservoir volumes	m ³	reservoir	Daily	Depending on the availability of data on the properties and management of the reservoirs.

3.6 AFOLU models

3.6.1 AFOLU: socio-economic inputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution	Source
Current cover	ha	100m	constant	CORINE, Scenario
Future cover	ha	100m	Annual	
Farm management operations parameters	NA	Case study	Sub annually	Scenario

3.6.2 AFOLU outputs

Variable	Units	Spatial domain and resolution	Temporal resolution	Comment
Yield (tree component)	kg/ha	Gridded, case study	Yearly	
Tree density (tree component)	tree m ⁻²	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Leaf development per shoot (tree component)	m ²	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Leaf area per tree (tree component)	m ² tree ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	

Leaf area index (tree component)	$m^2 m^{-2}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Fraction light interception (tree component)	m^{-2}	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Potential growth (tree component)	$g tree^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Water reduced growth (tree component)	$g tree^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Actual growth accounting for respiration when in leaf (tree component)	$g tree^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Biomass per tree (tree component)	$g tree^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Number of shoots per tree (tree component)	$tree^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Water uptake (tree component)	$m^3 tree^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Volume of timber (tree component)	$m^3 tree^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Height (tree component)	m	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Diameter at breast height (tree component)	cm	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Pruned branchwood per tree (tree component)	$g tree^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Pruned branchwood (tree component)	$m^{-3} ha^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Number of harvested trees (tree component)	$tree m^{-2}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Timber volume of stand (tree component)	$m^3 ha^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Harvested timber (tree component)	$m ha^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Volume of branchwood (tree component)	$m ha^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Harvested branchwood (tree component)	$m ha^{-1}$	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Clear stem height (tree component)	m	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Canopy area (tree component)	%	Gridded, case study	Daily	

Fruit yield increment (tree component)	g tree ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Fruit yield (tree component)	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Tree timber biomass (tree component)	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Tree branch biomass (tree component)	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Total canopy biomass (tree component)	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Potential growth (crop component)	g m ⁻² crop	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Actual growth (crop component)	g m ⁻²	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Leaf area index (crop component)	m ² m ⁻²	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Biomass (crop component)	g m ⁻²	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Water uptake (crop component)	m ³ m ⁻²	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Total dry weight per cropped area (crop component)	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Yield per cropped area (crop component)	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Yield 2 per cropped area (crop component)	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Total weight per total area (crop component)	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Yield per total area (crop component)	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Volumetric water content (crop component)	mm mm ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
pF (soil water tension, defined as the log of the water potential in cm water)	log(cm)	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Potential evaporation	mm	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Actual evaporation	mm	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Flow to groundwater	mm	Gridded, case study	Daily	

Crop water uptake (crop component)	mm	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Tree water uptake (tree component)	mm	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Overhead irrigation application	mm	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Soil water deficit	mm	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Critical deficit irrigation (tree component)	mm	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Critical deficit irrigation (crop component)	mm	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Root Biomass (tree component)	g tree ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
Carbon Sequestration	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	
CO ₂ Sequestration	t ha ⁻¹	Gridded, case study	Daily	

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